

Synthesize, characterization and antitubercular activity of some thiazolidinones tethered with pyrazolone moiety

Cendil Kumar Arunachalam, Rekha Abraham and Sivajothi Vaiyapuri*

Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, The Oxford College of Pharmacy, Bangalore-560 068, India

E-mail : writetojothi@yahoo.co.in

Abstract : A microwave assisted cyclocondensation method has been developed for the synthesis of a series of thiazolidinones incorporated with pyrazolones. The compounds reported are characterized spectrally by FT-IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR, MS data and subjected to *in vitro* antitubercular activity screening by Lowenstein Jensen method against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* H37Rv (Acid Fast Bacilli) MTCC 200, using Isoniazid 0.2 mcg/ml in DMSO as standard. No. of CFUs was counted and % inhibition calculated. AUTODOCK 4, a suite of automated docking tools, was employed for *in silico* screening. All the synthesized compounds were docked with *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* RmlCepimerase (Rv3465). The docking study revealed the best fit Root Mean Square Difference (RMSD). Some of the compounds exhibited comparable activity. Study reveals that the stabilization or destabilization of the pyrazolone ring due to the presence or absence of electron donating or withdrawing group does not seem to decide the activity of the compound.

Keywords : 3-Methyl-5-oxy-pyrazol-1-yl substituted 4-oxo-thiazolidinones, *in silico* screening, *M. tuberculosis* RmlCepimerase (Rv3465), *in vitro* antitubercular activity.

Introduction

Small heterocycles bearing nitrogen and sulphur, as heteroatom, constitute the pharmacophore of many of the medicinally active compounds. Molecules with pyrazolone ring system have exhibited varied pharmacological activities like antitubercular¹, antimicrobial², anticancer^{3,4}, antiviral⁵, analgesic⁶⁻⁹, anti-inflammatory^{8,9}, antipyretic^{9,10}, ulcerogenic¹¹, lipid peroxidation¹¹. Literature review¹²⁻¹⁴ of the structure activity relationship studies, involving pyrazolone ring, suggests that position N-1, C-3, C-4 are essential for structure activity studies and C-3 should be attached to other heterocyclic rings for better pharmacological activity. Since *N*-substitution in pyrazolone exhibit biologically active compounds¹⁵, in the present study microwave assisted synthesis of pyrazolones incorporated with 4-thiazolidinones followed by *in vitro* screening for their antitubercular activity against *M. tuberculosis* H37Rv MTCC 200 by standard methodology is envisaged.

Experimental

Microwave irradiation was carried out using microwave oven (KENSTAR Model No. OM-9928c, microwave 1200 W, input range 230 V-ac 50 Hz, microwave

frequency 250 MHz). FT-IR spectra were recorded on a Tensor 27 spectrophotometer, Brukeroptik (Germany) using ATR method. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker spectrophotometer using TMS as an internal reference (chemical shift in δ ppm). Mass spectra were recorded on GC-MS QP5050A System (bench top quadrupole mass spectrophotometer). Melting points, uncorrected, were determined in open capillaries on a Thermo-nik melting point apparatus, Mumbai, India.

Synthesis of 5-methyl-2,4-dihydro-3H-pyrazol-3-one (RA-1) :

Ethylacetoacetate (EAA) (0.1 mol) was stirred with dropwise addition of hydrazine hydrate (0.1 mol) in absolute ethanol, temperature maintained at 60 °C, crystalline deposit separated. Further stirred for 1 h at room temperature, cooled in ice and filtered product (RA-1) formed.

Synthesis of ethyl-(3-methyl-5-oxo-2,5-dihydro-1H-pyrazol-1-yl)acetate (RA-2) :

To RA-1 (0.025 mol) in acetonitrile, added anhydrous potassium carbonate (0.5 g), stirred for 10 min. Added ethylchloroacetate (0.025 mol) and continued stirring at room temperature for 16 h. Filtered and filtrate distilled at reduced pressure, residue obtained washed with ice cold water to get colorless product (RA-2).

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Synthesis of 2-(3-methyl-5-oxo-2,5-dihydro-1H-pyrazol-1-yl)acetohydrazide (RA-3) :

A mixture of RA-2 (0.7 mmol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.7 mmol) in ethanol was microwave irradiated at 300 W for 4 min. After completion of reaction, mixture cooled and solvent evaporated off at room temperature to get white needle shaped crystals of (RA-3).

General method of synthesis of compounds RA 4a-4n :

RA-3 (1.0 mmol), aromatic/hetero aldehyde (1.2 mmol), thioglycolic acid (1.49 mmol) and DMF were taken and microwave irradiated at 300 W for 2 min. Reaction monitored by TLC, after completion of reaction, cooled and about 10 equivalents of water added, pure product (RA 4a-4n) obtained by recrystallisation from methanol/suitable solvent.

Antitubercular activity screening :

The *in vitro* antitubercular screening was done by Lowenstein Jensen method¹⁶ using Malachite Green dye. The organism used for the study was *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* H37Rv (Acid Fast Bacilli) MTCC 200 and was procured from the Institute of Microbial Technology, Chandigarh. Nutrient medium used was Lowenstein Jensen Nutrient Medium in tube slants. The test compounds were prepared in DMSO in three different concentrations (25, 50 and 100 mcg/ml) and used. Isoniazid in DMSO (0.2 µg/ml) was used as the standard.

The sterile media was stirred to get uniform cooling, to a temperature of 45–50 °C, and distributed into sterile screw capped tubes. Added 25, 50 and 100 µg/ml solutions of the test compounds and 0.2 µg/ml solution of the standard in separate screw capped tubes, mixed well. The tubes were arranged in slant position. The inoculated tubes were incubated at 37 °C for 28 days. After 28 days of incubation, number of colony forming units (CFU) was counted and % inhibition calculated (Percentage inhibition is the ratio of CFUs formed by Test to Standard × 100).

In silico screening :

Docking studies were performed using AutoDock 4 (Molecular Graphics Laboratory, The Scripps Research Institute, USA). Docking was applied to screen the compound against the specific target protein *M. tuberculosis* RmlCepimerase (Rv3465) which is essential for

mycobacterial cell-wall synthesis. Standard ligand isoniazid was docked for comparison. The test compounds showed best fit RMSD values of 0.0000. Among all, RA-4d (with 4-nitrophenyl substitution), showed high affinity and low energy of –6.2 kcal/mol, compared with Isoniazid which scored a low energy value of –4.4 kcal/mol with a RMSD value of 0.0000.

Results and discussion

In silico screening of the pyrazolones reported revealed that all the compounds showed best fit (RMSD) value with *M. tuberculosis* RmlCepimerase Rv3465. The title compounds, RA 4a-4o (Table 1), varied in yield from 37.03 to 87.34%. Aldehydes with hydroxyl, methoxy group substitution either alone or together generally reduced the yield; heteroaldehyde (furaldehyde) produced the lowest. The bands appearing at around 3320, 1738 and 1670 cm⁻¹ in FT-IR spectra of all the compounds indicate the presence of -NH stretch, -C=O stretch and -CONH stretch respectively. The absence of a band at around 1500 cm⁻¹ in RA-2 in comparison to RA-3 indicates the conversion of -COOC₂H₅ into -CONHNH₂. A singlet at δ 4.6 (2H) indicates the presence of -N-CH₂CO group due to the substitution at N₁ in pyrazolone moiety. The broad sin-

Scheme 1

Table 1. Physical data of the compounds synthesized (RA 4a-4o)

Compound code	Ar	Molecular formula	Mol wt.	(%) Yield	M.p. (°C)	R _f ^a
RA-4a	Phenyl	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₃ S	332.38	87.34	218–220	0.75
RA-4b	2-Nitrophenyl	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ N ₅ O ₅ S	377.37	81.08	210–212	0.69
RA-4c	3-Nitrophenyl	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ N ₅ O ₅ S	377.37	75.67	246–248	0.72
RA-4d	4-Nitrophenyl	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ N ₅ O ₅ S	377.37	83.78	236–238	0.68
RA-4e	4-Chlorophenyl	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ ClN ₄ O ₃ S	366.82	75.0	226–228	0.65
RA-4f	<i>N,N</i> -Dimethylaminophenyl	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ N ₅ O ₃ S	375.4	86.48	236–238	0.58
RA-4g	4-Methylphenyl	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₃ S	346.4	85.29	228–230	0.67
RA-4h	4-Methoxyphenyl	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₄ S	362.4	44.4	230–232	0.62
RA-4i	4-Hydroxyphenyl	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₄ S	348.38	79.4	170–172	0.59
RA-4j	2-Hydroxyphenyl	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₄ S	348.38	51.72	236–238	0.60
RA-4k	2-Phenylethenyl	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₃ S	358.41	69.83	202–204	0.65
RA-4l	2-Furyl	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₃ S	322.34	40.37	206–208	0.67
RA-4m	3,4,5-Trimethoxyphenyl	C ₁₈ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₆ S	422.45	80.56	188–190	0.70
RA-4n	2-Naphthenyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₃ S	382.44	78.94	210–212	0.63
RA-4o	4-Hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₃ S	378.4	37.03	206–208	0.61

^aMobile phase – Ethanol : Petroleum Ether 2 : 1 v/v).

glet at around δ 9.5 (1H) indicates the -NH in the ring. The above facts indicate the formation of the compounds which was further confirmed by the *m/z* value of the respective M⁺ ions formed. Results of the *in vitro* antitubercular activity of the test compounds (Table 2) reveal that the type of substitution in the 2nd position of 5-pyrazolone moiety decides their activity.

The title compounds (Table 1) were synthesized as per Scheme 1.

Table 2. Results of *in vitro* antitubercular activity of compounds RA 4a to 4h

Sr. no.	Compd. code	% Inhibition		
		25 μ g/ml	50 μ g/ml	100 μ g/ml
1.	RA-4a	03	10	25
2.	RA-4b	12	21	33
3.	RA-4c	25	52	88
4.	RA-4d	32	58	92
5.	RA-4e	08	47	64
6.	RA-4f	24	41	78
7.	RA-4h	25	52	92
8.	Isoniazid	98% at 0.2 μ g/ml		

Conclusion

The stabilization or destabilization of the pyrazolone ring, because of the presence or absence of electron donating or withdrawing groups on the phenyl ring, does

not seem to decide the activity of the compound as both RA-4d and 4h, with *p*-nitrophenyl and *p*-methoxy phenyl group respectively, in the 2nd position of the pyrazolone ring, show an equal action (92% inhibition) comparable to the standard Isoniazid (98%).

It can be generalized that the presence of a nitro group either in the *meta* or *ortho* position on the phenyl at 2nd position of the pyrazolone group is preferred for antitubercular activity (88 and 33% inhibition respectively). Presence of other electron withdrawing group, parachloro, has produced a lesser action (64% inhibition) when compared to the nitro.

The requirement of a substituted phenyl, instead of an unsubstituted phenyl, (RA-4a), at the 2nd position of the pyrazolone moiety is preferred as the later has produced only 25% inhibition. The above findings are promising and will be of use in the designing of newer antimycotic compounds.

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